

Read me: Efficient scaling and squaring method for the matrix exponential

Sergio Blanes Nikita Kopylov Muaz Seydaoğlu

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We have presented a new algorithm in [1] to approximate the matrix exponential function for different tolerances at a lower computational cost than standard methods. In combination with scaling and squaring, this yields a procedure to compute the matrix exponential up to the desired accuracy at lower computational cost than the standard Padé method for a wide range of matrices.

This algorithm computes the matrix exponential within a given tolerance. Combined with the scaling and squaring procedure, the algorithm incorporates Taylor, partitioned and classical Padé methods shown to be superior in performance to the approximants used in state-of-the-art software. We analyse an extensive set of Taylor and rational Padé methods, we get error bounds for a set of tolerances and, taking into account their computational cost, we select a list of methods which our algorithm uses according to the provided matrix A and the tolerance tol . The algorithm has been written as two different Matlab code for different cases with name `expm_1.m` (partitioned non-diagonal Padé) and `expm_1diagpad.m` (partitioned diagonal Padé) that is available at the web page www.XXXXX.com.

One simply has to download the file and, given a A one just has to replace `expm(A)` by `expm_1(A)` or `expm_1diagpad(A)`. The new algorithm provides similar accuracy but, in general, at a reduced number of products.

We illustrate in a very simple example how the functions are used.

0.1 Example

We consider the matrix of normally distributed random number $A \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ defined as

$$A = \text{randn}(N)$$

The file `Example_0.m` define these matrices and compute the exponentials e^A with `expm` and for a given tolerance with `expm_1` and `expm_1diagpad`

```
E0=expm(A);
E1=expm_1(A,tol);
E2=expm_1diagpad(A,tol);
```

It provides as the output the difference between these solutions and we can observe that similar accuracies (about roundoff accuracy) are obtained using our new schemes which are faster in terms of number of matrix-matrix products.

References

- [1] S. BLANES, N. KOPYLOV AND M. SEYDAOĞLU, *Efficient scaling and squaring method for the matrix exponential*. arXiv:2404.12789, 2024.